

Synthesis and Characterisation of Lanthanide(III) Halide Complexes of 4-[N-(*p*-Dimethylaminobenzalidene)amino]-antipyrine

R. K. AGARWAL*, ARUN KUMAR, BHARAT BHUSHAN and RAM PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, Lajpat Rai (Post-Graduate) College, Sahibabad-201 005 (Ghaziabad)

Manuscript received 1 June 1992, revised 3 February 1994, accepted 9 February 1994

The complexing effect of various lanthanide ions with aromatic Schiff bases has been studied¹. The coordinating ability of the Schiff base 4-*N*-(*p*-dimethylaminobenzalidene)aminoantipyrine (DABAAP) formed by condensation of 4-aminoantipyrine and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde has been reported² toward thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI). The present work reports the results of our studies on the complexes of DABAAP with lanthanide(III) chlorides and bromides.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are coloured and fairly stable at room temperature. The 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry has been established on the basis of analytical results (Table 1). The molar conductance values in nitrobenzene at the concentration 10^{-3} M showed that the complexes are non-electrolytes. Magnetic moments indicate that in these complexes there is no metal-metal bonding and no spin-exchange occurs and hence they exist as monomers. These values also suggest that orbital contribution is almost quenched by the crystalline field. The plot of magnetic moments of these complexes against the atomic numbers of lanthanides shows the usual unequal double humped curve with the maximum lying at dysprosium complex³.

The $\nu_{C=O}$ bands occurring as doublet at 1 650, 1 645 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of the free ligand shifted to 1 600–1 590 cm^{-1} in all the complexes suggesting coordination of the metal ion through the oxygen atom of the free base^{4,5}. Another ligand band at 1 610 and 1 592 cm^{-1} ($C=N$)² shifted to lower wavenumber at 1 550–1 545 cm^{-1} , indicating the involvement of N-atom of the azomethine group on coordination^{4,5}. Some new medium and weak bands observed in the range 450–350 cm^{-1} in these complexes are tentatively as-

signed to $\nu_{Ln-O}/\nu_{I,n-N}$ modes^{3,6}.

The electronic spectra of the complexes (Table 2)

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Ln	N	C/I/Br		
DABAAP	—	—	—	—	—
La(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	15.11 (15.21)	12.13 12.26	11.58 11.65	4.1	Diamag.
Ce(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	15.23 (15.30)	12.14 12.24	11.57 11.64	3.9	2.60
Pr(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	15.31 (15.40)	12.13 12.23	11.57 11.63	3.2	3.60
Nd(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	15.57 (15.67)	12.08 12.19	11.52 11.59	5.0	3.59
Sm(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	16.13 (16.22)	12.01 12.11	11.45 11.51	4.6	1.65
Gd(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	16.73 (16.85)	11.96 12.02	11.36 11.43	5.1	7.86
Tb(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	16.94 (17.03)	11.93 11.99	11.33 11.40	4.9	9.21
Dy(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	17.23 (17.34)	11.87 11.95	11.28 11.36	4.8	10.50
Ho(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	17.44 (17.56)	11.81 11.92	11.24 11.33	5.2	10.46
Yb(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃	18.15 (18.25)	11.71 11.82	11.14 11.24	3.7	4.50
La(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	13.16 (13.27)	—	22.80 (22.92)	4.2	Diamag
Ce(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	13.24 (13.35)	—	22.78 (22.90)	3.8	2.58
Pr(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	13.33 (13.44)	—	22.75 (22.87)	3.6	3.59

Table 1 (Contd)

Nd(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	13 57 — (13 68)	22 67 (22 81)	4 9	3 62
Sm(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	14 06 — (14 17)	22 57 (22 68)	4 7	1 64
Gd(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	14 38 — (14 47)	22 42 (22 53)	4 9	7 94
Tb(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	14 80 — (14 90)	22 37 (22 49)	4 8	9 28
Dy(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	15 06 — (15 17)	22 29 (22 41)	4 6	10 51
Ho(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	15 25 — (15 37)	22 24 (22 36)	4 9	10 48
Yb(DABAAP) ₂ Br ₃	15 86 — (16 00)	22 09 (22 20)	3 8	4 49

in dioxane have been analysed to find out the use of nephelauxetic effect. The La^{III} and Ce^{III} complexes have no significant absorption in the visible region. The Pr^{III} complex exhibits four bands. There was a little difference in the molar absorptivities of the Sm^{III} complex and the samarium salt. But the difference in the case of the Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes was more pronounced. The various parameters like nephelauxetic parameter (β), Sinha's covalency parameter (δ) and bonding

parameter ($b^{1/2}$) have been calculated (Table 2). The positive values for $(1-\beta)$, δ and $b^{1/2}$ parameters in these complexes suggest that the bonding between metal and ligand is covalent as compared to that in metal-aquo ion.

In conclusion, the non-electrolytic behaviour of these complexes in conjunction with the IR spectral data suggest a coordination number seven for these complexes.⁷

Experimental

The ligand DABAAP was synthesised by refluxing (2 h) a mixture of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1 mmol) in absolute ethanol (40 ml) and 4-aminoantipyrene (1.1 mol) in the same solvent, then cooled and the resulting yellow solid was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 203–04°.

All the complexes were synthesised by the following general method. A methanolic solution of the ligand was refluxed (1 h) and then a methanolic solution of the trivalent lanthanide was added (1:2 ratio) to it. The mixture was then refluxed for ~ 2 h and then kept for slow heating on a hot plate till a thick layer of the precipitate settled. The supernatant liquid was decanted off. The resulting solid was dried under reduced pres-

TABLE 2 - ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) AND RELATED BONDING PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES DABAAP

Complex	λ_{\max} (nm)		J level	$(1-\beta)$	β	$b^{1/2}$	$\delta\%$
	LnCl ₃	Ln(DABAAP) ₂ Cl ₃					
Pr ^{III}	22 470	22 390	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂	0 003 56	0 996 4	0 042 19	0 357 2
	21 325	21 230	→ ³ P ₁	0 004 45	0 995 5	0 047 16	0 447 0
	20 750	20 620	→ ³ P ₀	0 006 26	0 993 7	0 055 94	0 629 9
	17 000	16 880	→ ¹ D ₂	0 007 05	0 992 9	0 059 37	0 710 0
Nd ^{III}	19 550	19 480	⁴ I _{9/2} → ² G _{9/2}	0 003 58	0 996 4	0 042 30	0 359 2
	17 360	17 260	→ ⁴ G _{5/2} , ² G _{7/2}	0 005 76	0 994 2	0 053 66	0 579 3
	13 660	13 630	→ ² S _{3/2} , ⁴ F _{7/2}	0 002 19	0 997 8	0 033 09	0 219 4
	12 470	12 430	→ ⁴ F _{5/2} , ⁴ H _{9/2}	0 003 20	0 996 7	0 040 00	0 321 0
Sm ^{III}	24 870	24 830	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ F _{9/2}	0 001 60	0 998 3	0 028 28	0 160 2
	24 000	23 835	→ ⁶ P _{5/2}	0 006 87	0 993 1	0 058 60	0 691 7
	21 550	21 520	→ ⁴ I _{13/2}	0 001 39	0 998 6	0 026 30	0 139 1
Ho ^{III}	22 300	22 200	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ G ₆ , ⁵ F ₁	0 004 48	0 995 2	0 047 30	0 450 1
	19 200	19 000	→ ⁵ F ₄	0 010 41	0 986 6	0 072 10	1 051 9
	15 700	15 500	→ ⁵ F ₅ , ⁵ S ₂	0 012 70	0 987 3	0 079 60	1 286 3
	13 500	13 250	→ ⁵ I ₄	0 018 51	0 981 5	0 096 20	1 885 8

NOTE

sure, washed with chloroform and methanol to remove any excess of the metal halide and/or ligand, and dried under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} . Analyses and physical measurements were performed as reported earlier⁶.

References

1. R. L. DUTTA and B. R. DAS, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1988, **47**, 547.
2. J. PRAKASH, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1990.
3. R. K. AGARWAL, *Asian J. Phys.*, 1992, **1**, 53.
4. R. K. AGARWAL and JAI PRAKASH, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 2399.
5. G. SHANKAR, R. R. PREMKUMAR and S. K. RAMALINGAM, *Polyhedron*, 1986, **5**, 991.
6. M. C. JAIN, R. K. SHARMA, A. K. SRIVASTAVA and P. C. JAIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 1305.
7. D. K. KOPPIKAR, P. V. SIVAPULLIAH, L. RAMAKRISHNAN and S. SOUNDARARAJAN, *Struct. Bonding*, 1978, **34**, 13, and references therein.

